

What are your Symptoms?

Factsheet #2

Large language models in healthcare and medicine

A TRANSFORMATIVE FORCE IN HEALTHCARE

The 2022 launch of OpenAI's ChatGPT has showcased the groundbreaking capabilities of Large Language Models (LLM) to a larger audience for the first time. Since then, public availability and scientific interest have resulted in a veritable flood of scientific works exploring possible areas of application.

A particularly rapid adoption of LLMs is seen in medicine and healthcare where researchers and practitioners alike explore the use of LLMs in clinical applications or to support patients in managing illness and disease as well as in public health, education of professionals or medical research.¹

Healthcare has seen a rapid adoption of LLMs in which researchers and practitioners explore potential scenarios of use.

A Swiss army knife of computational devices?

LLMs are stochastic computational models which, being trained on huge datasets of texts, are capable of processing and generating natural language. Simply put, LLMs predict the occurrence of the next word in a sentence based on information about the probability extracted from a corpus of data. Modern LLMs learn factors influencing this probability at an unprecedented scale resulting in models that can encompass billions of parameters. Combined with specific training approaches and model architecture, these machines have developed the capacity to accurately adapt to new tasks without being explicitly trained on them. This versatility has essentially turned LLMs into general purpose technologies.^{2,3} Such technolo-

LLMs and other general purpose technologies

gies are defined by their wide applicability across domains, their potential to trigger complementary innovations, and their ability to transform not only specific practices but entire sectors over time. Classic historical examples include electricity, the steam engine, or the internet—technologies that were not confined to one field of use but rather provided a foundational infrastructure upon which diverse new applications could be built. In a similar way, the nature of LLMs lies in this dual capacity for horizontal expansion — adapting across many different domains — and vertical improvement — continuously increasing efficiency, scale, and accuracy.

Applications in healthcare

Potential applications of LLMs in healthcare are varied and highlight the technology's versatility.⁴

Clinical applications

Clinical applications encompass, for example, their use in the initial diagnosis and triaging of patients or support in such tasks as predictive patient analysis and risk assessment. The envisioned role of LLMs in this context is often thought of as that of a co-pilot using available, often unstructured patient information to flag issues of concern or to predict risk factors and disease patterns. Many scholars hypothesize that this might directly contribute to patient benefit, especially in complex or time-sensitive environments such as emergency departments, where rapid assessments and decision support can improve outcomes. Beyond acute care, LLMs are also considered for longer-

als currently burdened with extensive administrative tasks. In a similar way, in research LLMs are suggested to support text or evidence summarization, assist in literature reviews, or facilitate knowledge sharing and collaboration across disciplines. Some researchers also highlight the potential for LLMs to act as research assistants in early stages of study design, hypothesis generation, or data interpretation.

Patient support applications

Patient support applications promise timely information and needs-oriented access, for example, through chatbots, to allow for access to comprehensible health information. In addition, LLMs could also provide personalized recommendations for treatment directly to patients, offer (initial) consultation, or bridge gaps between different healthcare settings. Examples include swift

Applications of Large Language Models in Health and Medicine

term treatment planning and chronic disease management, for instance by analyzing or monitoring longitudinal data from electronic health records.

Support of health professionals

LLMs could also be used to support health professionals and researchers directly. LLMs might be useful in streamlining clinical workflows through automation of repetitive tasks such as the population of reporting or discharging forms. This could offer valuable time savings for profession-

and easy cross-lingual provision of information, thereby removing communicative barriers, or mitigating obstacles in the clinical workflow. LLMs are also envisioned as tools to support patients in self-assessment and lifestyle management, which could foster patient engagement and health literacy.

Public health

Researchers in the field of public health discuss the use of LLMs in large-scale health campaigns and targeted health communication strategies.

In addition, the technology could be used for monitoring news and social media data to detect emerging disease patterns or to improve health literacy and access to health information. Beyond surveillance, LLMs may also contribute to global health equity by providing low-cost, scalable access to medical knowledge in under-resourced settings, thereby extending the reach of healthcare information and interventions to populations that have historically been underserved.

A recurring theme in debates about LLMs in medicine is the dissemination of wrong information which is seemingly correct but false in reality and is difficult to identify as such.

Evolving ethical patterns in the debate

Although the use of A.I. in general and of LLMs in particular brings much promise to the healthcare and medical fields, there is unanimous agreement that it also carries with it many ethical risks and issues which must be carefully addressed.

Epistemic implications of using LLMs

A recurring theme in the discussion are the epistemic implications of using LLM-generated output in healthcare settings. LLMs are known for “hallucinations”, i.e., to generate information which, although on the face of it plausible and presented with confidence, is in reality false. Furthermore, the nature of how LLMs work prevents the inspection of their internal reasoning processes, thus making their conclusions largely opaque and unintelligible for human decision makers. In addition, LLMs could lead to both unintentional and deliberate dissemination of inadequate or outright wrong information which are difficult to falsify. This reflects broader concerns about interpretability, transparency, and accountability that are also observed with other A.I. technologies. In healthcare, however, these ethical challenges are intensified by the field’s particularly stringent moral standards, professional obligations, and its tendency to generate complex dilemmas even without the introduction of potentially disruptive technologies.

Privacy and data security issues

Privacy and data protection form another important strand of discussion. LLMs are powerful because they can analyze vast amounts of information, recognize patterns in large datasets, and draw conclusions that would be impossible for a human to process alone. In healthcare, though,

this power depends on access to sensitive patient data. That raises serious questions – similar to those in the broader debate about digitalization – about privacy, security, and data ownership.

Since healthcare data is highly sensitive, concerns are also raised about how patient information is collected, stored, and possibly repurposed when used for training or interacting with commercial LLM systems. The role of commercial providers is itself contested, as the concentration of technological expertise and infrastructure in a few large companies raises issues of access, cost, and global equity.

Biases inherit to AI algorithms

Mirroring the issues with false information and “hallucination”, as well as questions of justice and equity, LLMs like all machine learning algorithms are particularly susceptible to biases. Since LLMs draw their conclusions from the analysis of and training on large datasets, these conclusions are fully determined by the content of these datasets. The availability of data is however endemically characterized by under- and misrepresentation of certain populations. LLMs in healthcare could therefore perpetuate harmful gender, cultural or racial biases, as well as vary in effectiveness and accuracy across different groups of people along different dimensions.

Uncontrolled experimentation and use

The use of LLMs in medicine and healthcare is characterized by a high degree of ambiguity and uncertainty, with some research being driven more by experimental curiosity rather than methodological rigor. A further theme raised in the discussions about LLMs in healthcare is, hence, the problem of uncontrolled experimentation. Because many LLM-based tools are already being trialed in healthcare settings without systematic evaluation or regulatory approval, their use risks exposing patients to technologies that have not been adequately tested. This blurs the

The exploratory use of LLMs in medicine is surrounded by uncertainty about the outcomes. However, exploration is often driven by curiosity rather than caution and rigor.

line between clinical research and practice, as experimental systems are sometimes deployed “in the wild” without the safeguards normally required for medical studies, such as informed consent or independent oversight. Such premature implementation may undermine patient safety and professional responsibility, calling for clearer frameworks to distinguish acceptable pilot testing from ethically problematic experimentation.

Future directions

To frame these developments and to allow for a safeguarded development of the technology in healthcare, it is helpful to consider the implementation of LLMs as a form of “social experiment”. This acknowledges the fact that full benefits, risks, and ethical issues of the technology become evident only after its widespread adoption. The uncertainties as well as the stakes involved in LLM-use in healthcare necessitates an iterative approach to their introduction, allowing for a gradual understanding of their actual consequences.

The speed at which both research surrounding LLMs has progressed in the past few years along with their rapid adoption by the general public as well as professionals and researchers across many fields, has prompted many to advise caution and emphasize the disruptive character of this technology. With that in mind, there is not only the need to familiarise oneself with such technologies and develop an understanding of their inner mechanics but also for vigilance towards new and emerging phenomena as well as for an iterative development of professional ethical guidelines. In particular, regarding LLMs, the ethical guidelines debate should focus on defining what constitutes acceptable human oversight and validation across the entire spectrum of LLMs’ possible applications and users.

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Read the full report

Haltaufderheide, Joschka; Ranisch, Robert (2024): The ethics of ChatGPT in medicine and healthcare: a systematic review on Large Language Models (LLMs). Available online at <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2403.14473>.

About the Digital Medical Ethics Network

Digitalization is rapidly changing the healthcare system and is having an increasing impact on practice. The use of new artificial intelligence technologies in diagnosis and therapy, mobile health applications on smartphones or the use of robotics holds a wide range of potential. However, it is also associated with ethical risks. Understanding these challenges and dealing with them is the task of medical ethics. Researchers need new knowledge and skills for this. The aim of the new Digital Medical Ethics Network (DiMEN) is to support them in this task by conducting research, developing freely available resources and strengthening networks among researchers. <https://www.digitalemedicalethics.net>

Recommendations for further reading

Dennstädt, Fabio; Hastings, Janna; Putora, Paul Martin; Schmerder, Max; Cihoric, Nikola (2025): Implementing large language models in healthcare while balancing control, collaboration, costs and

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